
MARKETING STRATEGIES IN DIGITAL AGE

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Abstract

The research paper shows the impact of various marketing strategies adopted by firms and how these marketing strategies have helped them to gain customer engagement as well to build their brands. There are a number of marketing strategies discussed and used by the firms. The introduction of PC's in 1970s marked the start of digital age and the marketing strategies along with digitization revolutionized the complete structure of marketing.

Keywords: Digital marketing, social media marketing, Influencer marketing, Search engine optimization, Organic marketing, Inorganic marketing, Leads, Sales funnel

Introduction

A marketing strategy is a long-term plan for achieving a company's goals by understanding the needs of customers and it also include to know your target audience and adopting channels so as to reach those customers. Marketing is not only just advertising or promotion but also connecting with customers and providing real time solutions to their queries. With the arrival of new age of technology, the methods of doing business and the various aspects of business have also evolved. The accounting done on physical books is replaced by the accounting done on computers on the software like tally. Letters had been replaced by E-mails. The meetings sometimes also don't even need to be take place in real physical form; it can also be done by the online meeting software like Zoom, Google Meet, and Skype. Similarly the world of marketing and sales had also gone through the timeline of evolution and had been changed. Now marketing is done more digitally than offline way. Basically, the motive of marketing is to make people know of the product either by offline marketing or online marketing. But online marketing has its own pros, which is why it is nowadays practiced more.

1. **Less cost-** digital marketing is a type of marketing which lets the firms to make people know about the product at a minimized cost.
2. **Adaptability and flexibility-** these digital marketing strategies are somewhere more easily to adapt and have more flexibility than offline marketing strategies.
3. **Wider reach-** online marketing strategies provide greater reach than offline marketing.
4. **More preference-** today's generation prefer online marketing more than offline marketing.

Talking about the history of digital marketing, the adoption of internet in 1990 led to the beginning of digital age. Then the introduction of SEO (Search Engine Optimization) marked its early days as a digital marketing strategy. Then, in the 2000s, Facebook, Twitter etc. were introduced which led to increase website traffic. In the 2010s, content marketing emerged as a strategy to increase digital marketing. These all introduction's further led to various AI models and shape the landscape of digital marketing strategies offering new opportunities for growth and innovation.

Literature Reviews

Kapoor, Sandeep (2014), an empirical study of online marketing in India- perspectives and challenges The marketing process progressed through three distinct eras like production that was prior to 1960s, sales that was after 1960s and then the strategic concept of marketing that was after 1990s. Internet marketing is the backbone of modern Capitalism. The internet will continue to affect marketing strategy in four broad ways:-

1. Through finer classification of segmentation
2. Through faster cycle time on marketing strategy development
3. Through increased accountability of marketing efforts

4. Through increased integration of marketing strategy with business strategy and operations.

Rekha (2018), Impact of digital marketing communication on consumer buying decision process: The behavior of consumer has undergone many changes in the digital age. One of the biggest channels of digital marketing are websites and social networking sites, which further include YouTube ,online communities and many more. Digital devices like mobile phones, computers, and digital TV etc. have also played an important role in increasing the value of digital marketing.

Bharath Sampath (2022), Impact of diffusion of digital marketing strategies on customer engagement, a study on MSMEs in Bengaluru In modern world, each firm or an enterprise wants to have its web presence for increased sales as well as better growth opportunities. India has seen a huge shift in increase of people from only offline marketing to online marketing as well.

Nair, K V Rajendran (2022), an analytical study on the digital marketing practices adopted at higher education institutions Digital marketing has a pivotal role in bringing a multi-cultured and multilingual society together on its various platforms by reducing the wide gaps and disparities of the socio-economic milieu. Technological advancement makes the modern business world swift and dynamic in the creation of plethora of opportunities by leveraging advanced tools to rise above the competition.

Objective

1. To study the conceptual framework of digital marketing
2. To study the benefits of digital marketing
3. To study the impact of digital marketing.

Hypothesis

Marketing strategies in digital age allows the firms to reach a wider audience, engage with customers effectively, analyze consumer behavior and help them with their queries in real time.

Research Methodology

1. Tools of analysis and presentation.

The tool of analysis and presentation used for the research are charts and graphs.

2. Data sources

The data used for the research is secondary data.

3. Research design

The research design of the paper is descriptive.

4. Period of study

The period of study in the research paper is mainly since 2015.

Conceptual Framework of Digital Marketing

Digital marketing brought a revolution with itself. Where, we were spending a lot of money and time in offline marketing to target the small group of customers, now we can target the large group of the target audience of our product and service with very affordable cost and even for the different and various parts of the world. Digital marketing is a very vast concept and includes various types of marketing in it:-

- Search engine optimization
- Social media marketing
- Search engine optimization

- Web analytics
- E-commerce management
- Planning and creating a website
- Email marketing
- Content strategy
- Affiliate marketing
- Influencer marketing

Each concept of the digital marketing is itself a different subject which has its own use, viability, necessity, importance and holds a long study to even master the one aspect of digital marketing.

That's why, a digital marketing agency has the employees who are expert in the different-different parts of digital marketing. Some have expertise in search engine optimization, some have in social media marketing and some have in Email marketing. But in the whole digital marketing, our main objective of this research is to find whether the social media marketing even helps the business to grow and increase its sale or just it only is an overrated trend of today's time.

Social media marketing is the way of marketing in which the business can reach out to its targeted audience and spread the awareness about its product/service in the way of content that can be in the form of text, picture, video that attracts the consumer towards the product or service via social media platforms like YouTube, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn etc.

Even in the social media marketing there are two types of marketing:-

1. Organic marketing
2. Inorganic marketing

Organic marketing is the way of social media marketing in which a brand starts to focus on building the personal brand on social media by uploading the content on their social media page which resonates with their audience and the product and the service provided by them to the consumers for some monetary amount.

Inorganic marketing is the way of marketing which is running paid ads on social media platforms to increase the product and service provided by the brand like Google ads, Meta ads etc.

Benefits of digital marketing in India

Both of the ways are used for the objective of increasing sales by using them as a sales funnel for the product and service.

Organic marketing helps the firms in the following ways:-

1. **Cost efficient-** organic marketing is a very cost efficient investment marketing and requires less amount of investment.
2. **Long term sustainability-** these marketing strategies are very effective for yielding long term results.
3. **Trust building** – these marketing strategies are very effective in trust building.
4. **Flexible-** organic marketing is a type of marketing which is very flexible and easy to adapt by firms.

Inorganic marketing strategies help the firms in following ways:-

1. **Fast results**-Google ads and social media ads are very helpful in giving fast results.
2. **Measurable results**- these marketing platforms provide tools which helps to measure various performances like ROAS, conversion rates etc.
3. **Scalable**- these strategies are of a nature that these are easy to scale.
4. **Target reach**- these marketing strategies help the firms to reach up to their targeted audience.

The impact of digital marketing

Digital marketing in India has put a great impact on the working of firms. Digital marketing has made it possible to advertise their product on their targeted audience efficiently. Moreover, customer engagement has also increased and it provided a greater reach for the businesses. Various channels for digital marketing in includes social media advertising platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, twitter and a lot more. Among all these, YouTube is one of the most customer engaging platforms.

Also, there are many channels for online brand research used by customers to gain knowledge about the products and services of a brand. The big channels used for the same are search engines, social networks, consumer reviews and many more.

The data presented above is the data of number of internet users, smart phone users and social network users. As the data stands, the numbers are increasing year by year. That is why, the website traffic is increasing and the brands can prosper themselves as well.

Years	internet users	smart phone users	social network users
2015	259.9	242.9	142.2
2016	295.4	281.8	168.1
2017	437.4	351.6	296.3
2018	483	390.9	326.1
2019	525.3	420.7	351.4
2020	564.5	448.2	376.1
2021	601	469.3	400.3
2022	634.9	486.7	422.7
2023	666.4	500.9	447.9

Table: No. of users of internet users, smart phones, social network users

As well as social media marketing as one the biggest mode of marketing where according to SEMRUSH, 63% of the respondents use paid channels to boom their content distribution where 73% of respondents shared that they use organic social media channels to promote their content.

From the various graphs and secondary data collected from different channels it can be analyzed that digital marketing has taken a boom in Indian regions. The data shown above shows that our assumption was true that social media marketing helps the businesses in increasing the sales and the leads of the business at very affordable cost.

Findings

1. Social media advertising is the second biggest market in digital ads (\$153 billion in 2021), after search advertising.
2. Google controls 28.6% of global digital ad spend, while Meta (FaceBook) is not far behind at 23.7%.

Conclusion

From the research carried out through various modes, it can be concluded that the marketing strategies evolved in the digital age has given an edge to its users. These marketing channels help them to accomplish more than one goal at the same time. These marketing has helped the firms a lot but have resulted in a disruption in the market.

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